

Soil Carbon and Nitrogen Enhancement through Co-Inoculation of *Bacillus subtilis* and *Bacillus fusiformis* with Rice Husk Amendment

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ABSTRACT

The study was conducted to investigate the influence of *Bacillus subtilis* and *Bacillus fusiformis* on soil total nitrogen amended with rice husk in the field, at Usmanu Danfodio University Teaching and Research Fadama Farm Kwalkwalawa, Wamakko Local Government Area, Sokoto State Nigeria. Soil samples were inoculated and collected after 42 days at a depth of 0-30cm with the aid of Auger to make a composite from each treatment. Three (3) samples were collected from each treatment making a total of nine composite (9) treatment samples. Samples were analyzed for total nitrogen and organic carbon. The result shows that *Bacillus subtilis* and *Bacillus fusiformis* do not differ with the sole application of rice husk, but rice husk differs significantly with the control treatment ($P \leq 0.05$). Rice husk recorded the highest soil organic carbon with a mean of (6.94 gkg^{-1}) followed by the combination of Rice husk + *B. subtilis* + *B. fusiformis* with a mean of (6.46 gkg^{-1}) and control has the lowest mean of (4.91 gkg^{-1}). Rice husk alone and Rice husk + *B. subtilis* + *B. fusiformis* recorded the highest mean values for soil total nitrogen with a mean of (0.10 and 0.12 gkg^{-1}) each and control has the lowest mean of (0.06 gkg^{-1}). This indicates *Bacillus* strains have the potential to be used for sustainable agricultural practices when amended with organic residues.

Keywords: *Bacillus subtilis*, *Bacillus fusiformis*, Organic Carbon, Total Nitrogen, Rice husk

INTRODUCTION

Bacillus subtilis and *Bacillus fusiformis* belonging to the group of Gram-positive, rod-shaped bacteria are part of the diverse and widespread *Bacillus* genus, with various species exhibiting different ecological roles and characteristics. Their properties and applications can vary significantly, depending on the specific strain and context in which they are found or used (Richs *et al.*, 2019). *Bacillus subtilis*, also known as "B. subtilis," is a common soil bacterium. It is often used as a model organism in microbiological research due to its well-characterized genetics and physiology (Barák, 2021). Considered a beneficial bacterium, it is commonly found in the soil and the gastrointestinal tracts of humans and animals (Freitas *et al.*, 2015). It is known for its ability to produce endospores, which are highly resistant structures that allow the bacterium to survive in harsh environmental conditions (Matthiesen, 2009).

Bacillus fusiformis is rod-shaped like other *Bacillus* species, and it can form endospores and different species of bacteria in the *Bacillus* genus. However, *Bacillus subtilis* appears to be more extensively studied than *Bacillus fusiformis* (Bhandari *et al.*, 2013; Savini, 2016; Monjer *et al.*, 2023). It is primarily found in marine environments and is often associated

with the decomposition of organic matter in marine sediments (Liu and Lee, 2007). Its role in nature is not as extensively documented as some other *Bacillus* species, and it is not as commonly used in industrial or research applications as *B. subtilis* (Andriyani *et al.*, 2021).

Nigeria, being an agricultural nation, heavily relies on rice production for food security and economic growth (Aihonsu and Adesini, 2006). However, the efficient utilization of nutrients in soil, particularly nitrogen, carbon, and phosphorus, is crucial for sustainable rice cultivation. Traditionally, chemical fertilizers have been used to meet the nutrient requirements of crops. However, this approach raises concerns about environmental sustainability and long-term soil health. To address these challenges, researchers have been exploring alternative approaches to enhance nutrient availability in soil. One promising avenue is the use of beneficial bacteria, such as *Bacillus subtilis* and *Bacillus fusiformis*. These bacteria have been found to play a vital role in nutrient cycling, soil fertility, and plant growth promotion (Kumari *et al.*, 2023).

Bacillus subtilis is known for its ability to fix atmospheric nitrogen, making it available for plant uptake. It also produces enzymes that break down organic matter, releasing carbon and other essential

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nutrients (Mshari *et al.*, 2019). On the other hand, *Bacillus fusiformis* is known for its phosphate-solubilizing abilities, which enhance phosphorus availability in soil (Delfim *et al.*, 2018). Understanding the influence of these bacteria on nutrient availability in soil will not only contribute to sustainable rice production but also provide valuable insights for the agricultural sector in Nigeria. It has the potential to improve soil health, increase crop productivity, and reduce the environmental impact of conventional farming practices (Delfim *et al.*, 2018). By harnessing the potential of these beneficial bacteria, we can reduce our reliance on chemical fertilizers and promote sustainable agricultural practices (He *et al.*, 2023).

The integration of rice husk as a bio-amendment adds a novel dimension to the discussion and bridges the knowledge gap using these bacteria and rice husk in soil amendment studies. Rice husk, an abundant byproduct of agriculture, is rich in carbon and silica. Rice husks when combined with *Bacillus subtilis* and *Bacillus fusiformis*, will create synergistic effects (Kovar and Cantarella, 2019). The carbon content of rice husk complements the extracellular enzymes produced by the bacteria, enhancing organic matter decomposition and nutrient cycling. Simultaneously, the silica content contributes to improved soil structure and water retention (Gill and Jalota, 2021). Rice husk, the outer protective layer of rice grains, is a byproduct of rice milling that has gained increasing attention in recent years due to its potential as a soil amendment (Kong and Lu, 2022). The objective is to study the influence of *Bacillus subtilis* and *Bacillus fusiformis* on soil nutrient dynamics when using rice husk as a soil amendment to enhance nutrient availability and foster overall soil health. This study will also test the hypothesis of whether the combination of rice husk with *Bacillus* strains will have any significant positive or negative effects on soil organic carbon and total nitrogen in soils.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted at University Fadama Teaching and Research Farm, Sokoto State Nigeria (Latitude 13°11' N, Longitude 5°15' E). The area is characterized by semi-arid vegetation, an average annual rainfall of 655.85 mm, and a mean temperature of 30°C (NIMET, 2022). Treatments included: (1) Control (no amendment), (2) Rice husk alone, and (3) Rice husk + *Bacillus subtilis* + *Bacillus fusiformis*, replicated three times in a randomized complete block design (RCBD). Soil samples were inoculated with strains of *B. Subtilis* and *B. fusiformis* for a long term (42 days) which is suitable for studying slow microbial processes, such as soil carbon sequestration or microbial-mediated nutrient cycling. Bacteria strains are sprayed directly to the soil in a liquid suspension

after mixing the powder 0.25 kg/ha with 200 litres of water in a separate container before filling it into the sprayer which was used within 6 hours from mixing based on the recommendations from the manufacturer NANDO Biological Products. Soil samples were collected from the study areas, at a depth of 0-30cm with the aid of Auger to make a composite from each treatment. The soil samples collected were properly labeled and stored in clean polythene bags for easy conveyance and to prevent any contamination. Soil samples were separately air-dried and crushed using a pestle and mortar in the laboratory. The ground soil samples were sieved with a 2mm sieve and the fine fractions were used for the determination of Total Nitrogen and Organic Carbon in the laboratory. Soil pH was measured in a 1:1 soil-water suspension using a glass electrode pH meter (Henders, 1993). Organic carbon was determined by the Walkley-Black wet oxidation method, with results expressed as % organic carbon (Nelson *et al.*, 2010). The formula used was:

$$\% \text{ organic carbon} = \frac{\text{MeK}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7 - \text{MeFeSO}_4 \times 0.003 \times 1.3}{\text{weight of the soil sample used}} \times 100$$

Data were analyzed using ANOVA, and means were separated using LSD at $P < 0.05$. Statistical analyses were performed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22.0.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Influence of *B. subtilis* and *B. fusiformis* on Soil Organic Carbon

The soil organic carbon (SOC) varied significantly across treatments (Table 1). The rice husk treatment recorded the highest SOC (6.94 g/kg), significantly higher than the control (4.91 g/kg) at $P \leq 0.05$. The combination of rice husk + *B. subtilis* + *B. fusiformis* showed slightly lower SOC (6.46 g/kg) compared to rice husk alone.

This increase in SOC with rice husk is attributed to its high organic carbon content (Linam *et al.*, 2023). The slight decrease in SOC in the combined treatment may result from microbial utilization of carbon as an energy source during mineralization (Malik *et al.*, 2020). This aligns with findings by Teutscherová *et al.* (2022), which highlighted increased microbial activity in organic residue-amended soils.

These findings suggest that the strains *Bacillus subtilis* characterize bacteria from rice processing sites have the potential for industrial applications (Su *et al.*, 2020). *B. subtilis* can decompose organic matter, releasing nutrients and solubilizing phosphorus, potassium, and other nutrients, making them available to plants (Singh *et al.*, 2011; Kumar *et al.*, 2014). *B. fusiformis* can form endospores and biofilms, which allow it to survive extreme environmental conditions, such as high temperatures, drought and adhere to soil particles and plant roots, promoting its survival and activity (Branda *et al.*, 2005; Nicholson, 2017). Overall, *B. fusiformis* plays a unique role in nutrient

cycling and soil health, contributing to the improvement of soil fertility, structure, and overall ecosystem function and the synergistic effects of combining rice husk with *Bacillus* strains.

Table 1. Influence of *Bacillus subtilis* and *Bacillus fusiformis* on soil organic carbon

Treatment	Organic carbon (gkg ⁻¹)
Control	4.91 ^c
Rice husk	6.94 ^a
Rice husk + <i>B. subtilis</i> + <i>B. fusiformis</i>	6.46 ^b
SE±	0.22
P. Value	0.00
Significance	*

Mean in a column followed by a similar letter (s) are not significantly different at 5% level of significance using least significant difference (LSD). * = Significant, SE± = Standard Error.

Influence of *B. subtilis* and *B. fusiformis* on Soil Total Nitrogen

The soil total nitrogen (TN) significantly increased in the rice husk and combined treatments compared to the control (Table 2). Rice husk alone and rice husk + *Bacillus* strains recorded TN values of 0.10 g/kg and 0.12 g/kg, respectively, while the control had 0.06 g/kg. Rice husk enhances TN by stimulating microbial activity and releasing nitrogen through decomposition (Sahoo *et al.*, 2018). The slight increase in TN in the combined treatment may reflect the nitrogen-fixing capability of *Bacillus subtilis* and its ability to improve nutrient cycling (Singh *et al.*, 2014).

Additionally, rice husk acts as a slow-release source of essential nutrients such as potassium, phosphorus, and calcium, thereby increasing nutrient availability in the soil and resulting in higher crop yields while reducing the need for synthetic fertilizers. Rice husk supplemented with *Bacillus subtilis* and *Bacillus fusiformis* did not significantly affect soil total N compared to the rice husk treatment but significantly affected soil total N compared to the control treatment. This may be attributed to the low-level N content of the rice husks and soil pH (Selvarajh *et al.*, 2020). Soil pH plays a crucial role in determining the availability and transformation of total nitrogen (TN) in soils with optimal pH ranges varying between 6.0 and 8.0 (Paul & Clark, 1996; Giller, 2001; Nannipieri *et al.*, 2012). In Acidic Soils (pH < 6.0) nitrogen availability is limited due to reduced microbial activity and increased ammonia volatilization (Fageria and Baligar, 2005), while in Neutral Soils (pH 6.0-7.0) optimal nitrogen

availability, as microbial activity and nitrogen mineralization are maximized (Havlin *et al.*, 2014). This was attributed to microbial growth which is optimal at pH range 6.0 and 7.0 for microbial growth and nitrogen mineralization (Stevenson, 1986; Paul, and Clark, 1996). This indicates soil pH plays a crucial role in nitrogen availability, as it affects the forms and transformations of nitrogen in the soil (Figure 1.).

Rice husk supplemented with *Bacillus subtilis* and *Bacillus fusiformis* did not significantly affect soil total N in tropical paddy soil (Kapilan and Arasaratnam, 2011). The bacteria *Bacillus subtilis* and *Bacillus fusiformis* play crucial roles in these processes. *Bacillus subtilis* decomposes organic matter, releasing carbon and nutrients into the soil, and benefiting other microbes and plants (Singh *et al.*, 2014). This bacterium also produces enzymes that break down complex organic molecules, contributing to soil organic matter cycling. *Bacillus fusiformis* similarly contributes to the cycling of organic carbon in soil by breaking down complex organic molecules such as lignin and humic substances (Singh *et al.*, 2017). These show not all but certain *Bacillus* species can fix atmospheric nitrogen into ammonia; a process that can increase soil pH due to the alkaline nature of ammonia, this nitrogen-fixing capability, and phosphorous availability contribute to soil fertility and overall plant growth (Abubakar and Muhammad, 2015; Singh *et al.*, 2017).

Table 2: Influence of *B. subtilis* and *B. fusiformis* on Soil Total Nitrogen

Treatment	Total Nitrogen (gkg ⁻¹)
Control	0.06 ^b
Rice husk	0.10 ^a
Rice husk + <i>B. subtilis</i> + <i>B. fusiformis</i>	0.12 ^a
SE±	0.03
P. Value	0.00
Significance	*

Mean in a column followed by a similar letter (s) are not significantly different at a 5% level of significance using least significant difference (LSD). * = Significant, SE± = Standard Error.

Figure 1: Relationship between Soil pH and Total Nitrogen

Conclusion

The results demonstrate that rice husk and bacterial amendments (*Bacillus subtilis* and *Bacillus fusiformis*) significantly improved soil organic carbon and total nitrogen compared to the control. However, the statistical similarity observed between treatments with rice husk alone and rice husk combined with bacterial inoculants suggests that the contribution of these bacterial strains to nitrogen dynamics in this study area may be limited under the given conditions. Nevertheless, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Bacillus fusiformis*

have shown potential as decomposers to enhance soil organic matter mineralization and nutrient cycling. These findings highlight the potential of integrating organic amendments and microbial inoculants to improve soil fertility in semi-arid agricultural systems. Further studies are recommended to explore long-term effects and optimize application strategies for broader adoption in Sub-Saharan Africa.

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